

VITAMIN C AND TOXINS. PART I. THE EFFECT OF VITAMIN C AND OTHER REDUCING SUBSTANCES ON DIPHTHERIA AND TETANUS TOXINS IN VITRO.

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The effect of vitamin C, glutathione, cysteine and hydroquinone on diphtheria and tetanus toxins *in vitro* has been investigated. The inactivating effect of ascorbic acid is differentiated from the inactivation due to lowering in pH .

The anti-infective properties of vitamin C have been the subject of investigation in different laboratories for some time. It has been shown that guinea-pigs kept on a ration deficient in vitamin C are less resistant to diphtheria toxin than normal animals (Jungeblut and Zwemer, *Proc. Soc. Biol. Med.*, 1935, 32, 1229; Jungeblut, *ibid.*, 1935, 32, 1039). King and Menton (*J. Nutrition*, 1935, 10, 122, 141; *ibid.*, 1935, 9, proc. II) have claimed that the resistance of guinea-pigs against diphtheria toxin is increased by administration of large doses of ascorbic acid given *per os* or by injection. Others (Widenbauer and Saretz, *Klin. Woch.*, 1936, 18, 1131; Polonyi, *Wien. Med. Wchnesch.*, 1935, 85, 685) have reported the inactivation of diphtheria toxin *in vitro* by vitamin C. Sigal and King (*J. Pharm. Expt. Therap.*, 1937, 89, 468), on the other hand, have stated that neutralised vitamin C is incapable of detoxicating diphtheria toxin *in vitro* and they conclude that the inactivation of the toxin by unneutralised ascorbic acid is probably due to the acidity of the solution and not due to the vitamin *per se*.

The present work was undertaken in order to study more fully the behaviour of diphtheria and tetanus toxins to vitamin C under different conditions and to throw light on the mechanism of inactivation. Since ascorbic acid is both a reducing substance and acidic in nature, it was considered desirable to study the behaviour of the toxins to other biologically active reducing substances and also to control the effect of the hydrogen ion concentration. In the present *in vitro* experiments we have studied the effect of vitamin C and of other reducing substances like glutathione, cysteine, hydroquinone, etc., and also the effect of pH on the inactivation of the toxins. A preliminary note on this subject giving some main results has been published elsewhere (Ghosh and Guha, *Science and Culture*, 1937, 3, 243).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Diphtheria and Tetanus Toxins and Ascorbic Acid.

A solution (1 c.c.) of the toxin in normal saline standardised to contain 1 m. l. d. of the toxin was mixed with 25 mg. of ascorbic acid and allowed to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature (27°) and the mixture injected subcutaneously into guinea-pigs weighing between 250 and 300 g. All the animals survived, remained healthy and gained in weight during the next two months—the period under observation—while the control animals died within 4 days as shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Nature of toxin.	Dose.	Number of animals		
		Treated.	Survived.	Died.
Diphtheria	1 m. l. d.	6	None	6
"	1 m. l. d. mixed with ascorbic acid (25 mg.)	6	6	None.
Tetanus	1 m. l. d.	6	None	6
"	1 m. l. d. mixed with ascorbic acid (25 mg.)	6	6	None

In the next series of experiment the effect of smaller quantities of ascorbic acid was investigated (Table II), which show that a small dose like 2 mg. is capable of inactivating the toxins.

TABLE II.

Toxin employed.	Ascorbic acid added to 1 m. l. d. toxin.	Number of animals	
		Treated.	Survived.
Diphtheria	10 mg	4	4
"	5	4	4
"	2	4	4
Tetanus	10	6	6
"	5	4	4
"	2	4	4

Diphtheria and Tetanus Toxins and Reducing Substances other than Ascorbic Acid.

Since ascorbic acid is a strongly reducing agent it was considered possible that the mechanism of inactivation involves the reduction of the toxins. In order to test this view other reducing substances like glutathione, cysteine and hydroquinone were employed. These substances were found to be equally capable of detoxicating the toxins. 25 Mg. of these reducing substances (glutathione, cysteine and hydroquinone) were mixed *in vitro* with the toxin and after standing at room temperature for 15 minutes injected into guinea-pigs, which showed no symptoms of toxicity subsequently. The detoxicating action of glutathione has been reported at about the same time by Vincent (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 1693; Binet, Janlmes and Weller, *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 1761; Ghosh and Guha, *loc. cit.*) The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Substances mixed with 1 m. l. d. toxin.	(a) Diphtheria toxin.			(b) Tetanus toxin.		
	Number of animals			Number of animals		
	Treated.	Survived.	Died.	Treated.	Survived.	Died
Glutathione (25 mg.)	6	6	None	6	6	None
Cysteine (25 mg.)	6	6	„	6	6	„
Hydroquinone (25 mg.)	6	5	1*	6	6	„
1 m. l. d. toxin alone	6	None	6	6	None	6

* Died after 10 days.

Diphtheria and Tetanus Toxins and p_{H} .

The following experiments were undertaken to control the effect of p_{H} . It was found that diphtheria toxin has a p_{H} near about 6.8, while that of tetanus toxin lies between 7.2 and 7.4. On addition of reducing substances (ascorbic acid, glutathione, cysteine and hydroquinone), the p_{H} of the mixture goes down to 2.8-1.4 (Table IV).

TABLE IV.

Diphtheria toxin	p_{H} .	Tetanus toxin	p_{H} .
	6.8		7.2-7.4
„ +25 mg. ascorbic acid	2.8	„ +25 mg. ascorbic acid	2.8
„ +25 mg. glutathione	2.8	„ +25 mg. glutathione	2.8

TABLE IV (contd.).

	p_H		p_H
Diphtheria toxin + 25 mg. cysteine	1.4	T. Toxin	+ 25 mg. cysteine 1.4
" + 25 mg. hydroquinone	3.5	"	+ 25 mg. hydroquinone 3.5

In order to investigate whether simple lowering of the p_H of the toxin can effect detoxication, a drop or two of hydrochloric acid was added to the saline solution of the toxin so that the final p_H lay at about 2.8. It was found that the toxins were completely inactivated. Six animals injected with the acidified diphtheria toxin and 5 animals injected with the acidified tetanus toxin—all survived, while five control animals injected with toxin alone died within 3 days.

The effect of different hydrogen ion concentrations on the activity of the toxin was next studied. A large number of experiments were carried out with citrate-phosphate buffer (McIlvaine) varying in p_H from 4.6 to 6.8 and it was found that below p_H 5.0, both tetanus and diphtheria toxins are inactivated, while above this p_H they remain active.

TABLE V.

p_H .	(a) Diphtheria toxin.			(b) Tetanus toxin.		
	Number of animals Treated.	Survived.	Died.	Number of animals Treated.	Survived.	Died.
4.6	6	6	None	—	—	—
5.0	6	6	"	6	6	None
5.4	6	None	6	6	None	6
6.0	6	"	6	—	—	
6.8	6	"	6	6	None	6

Since at p_H 5.4 both the toxins are active, it was considered desirable to know whether ascorbic acid brought to p_H 5.4 by addition of sodium hydroxide would have any inactivating effect on the toxins at p_H 5.4. It is clear that if it is so, the detoxicating effect of vitamin C cannot merely be due to acidity but is probably due to the action of the vitamin *per se*. Ascorbic acid was, therefore, dissolved in saline or citrate-phosphate buffer at p_H 5.4 and caustic soda was added to bring the p_H back to 5.4, then the toxin was added, the final p_H was checked to be 5.4 and the mixture injected into animals. These experiments were carried out with toxin and all the animals so treated survived (Table VI). This would indicate that in the case of diphtheria toxin, ascorbic acid has some action apart from acidity—a view which is supported by Jungeblut (*J. Immunol.*, 1937, 33, 203) in his experiments with tetanus toxin.

The effect of ascorbic acid raised to p_H 6.8 on the toxin was also studied to see if the vitamin will have any inactivating effect near the neutral zone, but with both the toxins the effect of the vitamin was found to be nil at this p_H .

TABLE VI.

	(a) Diphtheria toxin.		
	Treated.	Survived.	Died.
Ascorbic acid at p_H 6.8	6	None	6
„ „ „ 5.4	6	6	None
(in citrate-phosphate buffer)			
Hydrochloric acid at p_H 5.4	5	„	5
Toxin at p_H 5.4 (in citrate-phosphate buffer) ...	6	„	6
(b) Tetanus toxin.			
Ascorbic acid at p_H 6.8	6	„	6

CONCLUSION.

(1) The effect of vitamin C in different quantities on diphtheria and tetanus toxins *in vitro* was investigated and it was found that 2 mg. of the vitamin mixed with 1 m. l. d. of the toxin was able to cause inactivation.

(2) Similar inactivating effect was also observed with other reducing substances—glutathione, cysteine and hydroquinone.

(3) The effect of p_H on the toxin was studied and it was found that the lowering of p_H results in quick inactivation.

(4) Diphtheria toxin at p_H 5.4 is active but it is detoxicated at the same p_H in the presence of ascorbic acid. This indicates that the effect of ascorbic acid is at least partially due to the effect of ascorbic acid *per se* and not merely a p_H effect.

(5) At p_H 6.8 ascorbic acid has no inactivating effect on the toxin studied.

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